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A Research Article

OUTCOMES OF PNEUMATIC LITHOTRIPSY VERSUS HOLMIUM LASER IN DISTAL URETERIC STONES

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Abstract:

Objective: To compare the outcomes of pneumatic lithotripsy versus holmium laser in distal ureteric stones

Study Design: Cross sectional study

Setting & Duration of Study: The study was conducted at department of Urology in Sindh Institute of Urology and Transplantation (SIUT) Karachi. Six months. Since 1st July 2020 till 31st December 2020.

Method: 208 patients who underwent Pneumatic Lithotripsy and Holmium Laser in Distal ureteric stones were selected for the study, who were randomized into 2 groups of 104, in each group the success rate in the pneumatic group and in laser group is calculated. Outcomes were assessed in terms of intra-operative time period, stone migration, need for stent placement, hospital stay and stone clearance.

Results: There were total 208 cases of mean age of 37.15±9.14 years. When they were evaluated for stone size mean size of stone was 8.9±2.24mm of which the mean stone size of pneumatic lithotripsy was 8.50±2.21 and in the Ho: YAG laser group was 9.13±2.22. On comparison, it was noted that pneumatic lithotripsy was effective in 65 (62.5%) and Ho: YAG laser in 89 (85.57%) with a statistically significant difference (p< 0.06). On stratification, it was noted that there is no significant impact of age on the efficacy of the treatment. Ho: YAG laser was effective in 71 (79.77%) in age group <30 and showed the results of Ho: YAG laser 18 (20.22%) in >40 year of age. But there was significant difference for the size of stone in the treatment groups with a p-value of <0.05 as significant.

Conclusion: Outcomes are better in patients of ureteric stones having laser lithotripsy as compared to the patients having pneumatic lithotripsy.

Keywords: Pneumatic lithotripsy, Laser lithotripsy, ureteric stone

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INTRODUCTION:

Urolithiasis is one of the leading causes of morbidity of the urinary tract system in the world. Within the last few decades, the treatment of urinary tract stones has been revolutionized due to introduction of minimally invasive techniques [3]. Urinary tract stones especially ureteric stones can present as emergency to urologists [1]. A variety of treatment options are available for ureteric calculi but there is increasing trend towards minimal invasive surgery. With the advent of continuous refinements in minimally invasive techniques, open surgery is becoming a procedure of the past [1]. Traditionally, URL (ureteroscopic lithotripsy) has been preferred for the treatment of stones in the lower and mid ureter and SWL (shockwave lithotripsy) has been preferred more for the treatment of stones in the upper ureter [1]. The different modalities of intra corporeal lithotripsy are lasers, pneumatic lithoclast, electro hydraulic (EHL) and ultrasonic lithoclast [1]. Lithoclast lithotripsy and holmium:YAG lithotripsy have reported favorable outcomes. A rather simple principle of the jackhammer has enabled Lithoclast lithotripsy to be a safe and effective method for stone treatment [1,2]. Thus, the Lithoclast has become a widespread tool for fragmentation of urinary stones. However, it has some disadvantages. Semirigid probe requires a rigid or at least a semirigid ureteroscope and there is a high possibility of undesired retrograde displacement of the calculus [1,2]. Aim of this study is to compare the outcomes of holmium: YAG laser and pneumatic lithoclast in treating distal ureteric calculi. Intraoperative time period will be assessed in minutes. Stone migration into upper ureter or kidneys will analyzed intraoperatively under fluoroscope and possible need for double j stent or ureteric catheter placement will be decided accordingly. Hospital stay will be quantified in days. The clearance of renal stone with no residual fragments or fragments under 4 mm after treatment is defined as stone clearance. This will be determined by x-ray and ultrasound KUB one week and 4 weeks after procedure.

METHOD:

208 patients who underwent Pneumatic Lithotripsy and Holmium Laser in Distal Ureteric Stones were selected for the six study, from 1st July 2020 to 31st December 2020 who were randomized into 2 groups of 104, in each group the success rate in the pneumatic group and in laser group is calculated. Outcomes will be assessed in terms of intra-operative time period, stone migration, need for stent placement, hospital stay and stone clearance.

The inclusion criteria include age 18-60 years, unilateral distal ureteric stones, stone size 0.8 to 1.5 cm, radio-opaque stones.

Pediatric age group, pregnant lady, active UTI, distal ureteric stone having size less than 0.8 cm and greater than 1.5 cm, stone located in location other than distal ureter, coagulopathy, patients not willing were excluded from study.

After approval from research evaluation unit and ethical committee of the hospital, 200 patients who were present in urology department of Sindh Institute of Urology and Transplantation fulfilling the inclusion criteria were included in this study. An informed consent was taken from all patients before including them in this study. Procedures was done by senior surgeons having experience of at least 5 years after fellowship. Post-procedural X-ray KUB was done 4 weeks after the surgical procedure to determine the stone clearance in every patient. There were 2 groups. All pts who undergoes pneumatic procedure were included in group 1 and group 2 for those pts having laser procedure. All the gathered information regarding stone clearance and other relevant information regarding patient's age, gender, and duration of renal stone disease was recorded on a pre-designed Proforma.

Data analysis was entered and analyzed by using SPSS v20.0. Mean and standard deviations was calculated for quantitative variables like age, duration of renal stone disease, height, weight. Categorical variables like intra-operative time period, stone migration, need for stent placement, hospital stay and stone clearance was presented as frequency and percentage. Chi-square test was used to compare stone clearance between groups. Stratification of confounder variables e.g. age, gender, duration of renal stone disease, and location of calculi was done. P-value ≤ 0.05 was considered as significant.

RESULTS:

There was total 208 cases of mean age of 37.15 ± 9.14 years (Table 1). When they were evaluated for stone size mean size of stone was 8.9 ± 2.24 mm of which the mean stone size of pneumatic lithotripsy was 8.50 ± 2.21 and in the Ho: YAG laser group was 9.13 ± 2.22 (Table 2).

On comparison, it was noted that pneumatic lithotripsy was effective in 65 (62.5%) and Ho: YAG laser in 89 (85.57%) with a statistically significant difference ($p < 0.06$) (Table 3).

On stratification, it was noted that there is no significant impact of age on the efficacy of the treatment. Ho: YAG laser was effective in 71 (79.77%) in age group <30 and showed the results of Ho: YAG laser 18 (20.22%) in >40 year of age (Table 4).

But there was significant difference for the size of stone in the treatment groups with a p-value of <0.05 as significant (Table 5).

Table 1: Distribution of Mean Age in the study participants

	Group of treatment	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Age of patients	Pneumatic Lithotripsy	104	34.40	9.68
	Holmium YAG Laser	104	39.90	8.6

Table 2: Distribution of Size of stone in the study participants

	Group of treatment	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Stone size	Pneumatic lithotripsy	104	8.5	2.28
	Holmium YAG laser	104	9.3	2.2

Table 3: Comparison of efficacy of treatment in the both groups

		Efficacy of the treatment		Total
		Achieved	Not achieved	
Group of treatment	Pneumatic lithotripsy	65	39	104
		62.50%	37.5%	100%
	Holmium YAG laser	89	15	104
		85.57%	14.42%	100%

Table 4: Stratification of age of treatment for the ureteric stone

Age group	Group of treatment	Efficacy of the treatment		Total	P value
		Achieved	Not achieved		
18- 30 years	Pneumatic lithotripsy	41	15	56	0.642
		63.1%	38.5%		
	Holmium YAG laser	71	2	73	
		79.77%	13.33%		
>30 years	Pneumatic lithotripsy	24	24	48	0.604
		36.9%	61.53%		
	Holmium YAG laser	18	13	31	
		20.22%	86.66%	100%	

Table 5: Stratification of stone size of treatment for the ureteric stone

Size of stone	Group of treatment	Efficacy of the treatment		Total	P value
		Achieved	Not achieved		
6-10mm	Pneumatic lithotripsy	49	12	61	0.05
		75.4%	30.7%		
	Holmium YAG laser	80	3	83	
		89.88%	20%		
>10mm	Pneumatic lithotripsy	16	27	43	0.06
		24.6%	69.2%		
	Holmium YAG laser	9	12	21	
		10.11%	80.0%		

DISCUSSION:

The -holmium: YAG laser has excellent stone fragmenting properties and as a result, it is now a well-established modality for intracorporeal lithotripsy [11-13]. Holmium laser light can be transmitted through a thin, flexible fiber compared with instruments for mechanical stone fragmentation. Holmium: YAG lithotripsy depends on photothermal mechanism for stone fragmentation, thus the risk of retrograde stone propulsion could be minimized, but it may cause thermal injury to the ureter if used carelessly [14]. Holmium: YAG laser is a budding modality for treatment of urinary stones in Pakistan and this study would be an effort to introduce modern methods for combating heavy burden of Urolithiasis in this part of the world [14].

At the aspect of mean operative time, early and delayed stone-free rate, LL is superior to PL. Laser lithotripsy is superior to pneumatic Lithotripsy at the aspect of mean operative time, early and delayed stone free rate [16]. Laser lithotripsy is better than Pneumatic lithotripsy in stone free rate and safe in proximal ureteric stones[17].

Any type of lithotripsy has no much difference in stone free rate of ureteral stone but Laser lithotripsy is expensive [18]. YAG laser has higher stone free rate in immediate post op Lithotripsy then pneumatic Lithoclast [19]. Laser lithotripsy in upper ureteral stones provides good stone free rate in children and adults.¹ Combine Pneumatic lithoclast and laser lithotripsy decrease the complication rate and redo URS in impacted uretral stones [20]. Laser lithotripsy is expensive but more effective in than pneumatic Lithotripsy [22]. Holmium YAG laser lithotripsy is more effective than Pneumatic lithoclast lithotripsy in immediate uretral stone free rate [23,24].

Ethical Approval

IRB Number: 240

Approval No: SIUT-IRB-240

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